

Synthesis, antitubercular and antimicrobial activities of some new pyrazoline and isoxazole derivatives

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Abstract : Cyclocondensation of hydrazine hydrate with (2*E*)-1-(3,5-dibromo-4-methoxyphenyl)-3-aryl-prop-2-en-1-ones (1*a-j*) in glacial acetic acid afford corresponding 1-acetyl-3-(3,5-dibromo-4-methoxyphenyl)-5-aryl-4,5-dihydro-1*H*-pyrazoles (2*a-j*). While the compounds 1*a-j* on reaction with hydroxylamine hydrochloride in presence of acetic acid and sodium acetate to give 3-(3,5-dibromo-4-methoxyphenyl)-5-aryl-isoxazoles (3*a-j*). All the compounds were tested against different microbes for their antimicrobial activity and compounds 2*a-j* were tested for antitubercular activity.

Keywords : Pyrazolines, isoxazoles, microbial activity.

Pyrazolines and isoxazoles consists a unique class of five member rings containing nitrogen and oxygen heterocycles. There has been considerable interest in the pyrazoline ring system and isoxazole ring system, both with regard to heterocyclic chemistry and pharmacological activities of several of its derivatives. Pyrazolines and isoxazoles have been studied extensively because of ready accessibility, diverse chemical reactivity, broad spectrum of biological activities such as antimicrobial¹, cytotoxic agent², anti-inflammatory³, antitumor⁴, anticonvulsant⁵, anti-tubercular⁶, tyrosine phosphatase 1B inhibitors⁷ and anti-HIV⁸ etc. Looking to these multifold properties exhibited by them, we are reporting here the synthesis and biological activity of some new pyrazolines (2*a-j*) and isoxazoles (3*a-j*) derivatives. In the present study, we use this strategy for the synthesis of these compounds in the hope that they may possess potential biological activities.

Condensation of different aryl aldehyde with 3,5-dibromo-4-methoxy acetophenone in presence of 40% alkali yielded corresponding (2*E*)-1-(3,5-dibromo-4-methoxyphenyl)-3-aryl-prop-2-en-1-one⁹ (1*a-j*) which on condensation with hydrazine hydrate gives 1-acetyl-3-(3,5-dibromo-4-methoxyphenyl)-5-aryl-4,5-dihydro-1*H*-pyrazoles⁹ (2*a-j*) and further compounds 1*a-j* on reaction with hydroxylamine hydrochloride in acidic buffer solution yielded 3-(3,5-dibromo-4-methoxyphenyl)-5-aryl-isoxazoles¹⁰ (3*a-j*).

The structures of the synthesized compounds were assigned on the basis of elemental analysis, IR, ¹H NMR

and mass spectral data. All newly synthesized compounds have been screened for their *in vitro* antimicrobial activity and compounds 2*a-j* for their antitubercular activity (Table 1).

Results and discussion

Antitubercular activity :

The antitubercular evaluation of the compounds was carried out at Tuberculosis Antimicrobial Acquisition Coordinating Facility (TAACF), USA. Primary screening of the compounds for antitubercular activity has been conducted at 6.25 µg/ml against *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* H₃₇Rv ATCC 27294, in BACTEC 12B medium using the ALAMAR radiometric system.

The antitubercular activity data were compared with standard drug Rifampin at 0.25 µg/ml concentrations, which showed 98% inhibition (Table 1).

Antimicrobial activity :

The antimicrobial activity was assayed by using the cup-plate agar diffusion method¹¹ by measuring the zone of inhibition in mm. All the compounds were screened *in vitro* for their antimicrobial activity against varieties of bacterial strains such *Bacillus megaterium* ATCC 14518, *Bacillus subtilis* ATCC 23837, *Escherichia coli* ATCC 25922, *Proteus vulgaris* ATCC 29213 and fungi *Aspergillus niger* ATCC 9029 at 40 µg/ml concentration. Standard drugs like Ampicillin, Amoxicillin, Norfloxacin, Benzyl penicillin and Greseofulvin were used for the comparison purpose (Table 1).

Table 1. Antitubercular and antimicrobial screening results of compounds **2a-j** and **3a-j**

Compd.	R	% Inhibition Antitubercular activity	Zones of inhibition in mm				
			Antibacterial activity				Antifungal activity
			<i>B. mega</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>P. vulgaris</i>	<i>A. niger</i>
2a	3-Br-C ₆ H ₄ -	19	12	18	18	9	4
2b	2-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	27	14	22	12	8	20
2c	4-N(CH ₃) ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	13	21	14	14	14	14
2d	4-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	10	8	3	10	10	18
2e	2-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	34	22	16	10	10	18
2f	3-C ₆ H ₅ -C ₆ H ₄ -	18	13	5	14	9	8
2g	2-OH-C ₆ H ₄ -	16	20	22	16	10	14
2h	4-OH-C ₆ H ₄ -	19	8	13	5	12	22
2i	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	22	18	10	16	15	12
2j	3-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	12	21	16	10	14	20
3a	3-Br-C ₆ H ₄ -	-	18	14	13	17	16
3b	2-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	-	17	9	12	19	8
3c	4-N(CH ₃) ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	-	5	16	10	10	14
3d	4-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	-	16	22	12	14	12
3e	2-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	-	5	11	10	10	10
3f	3-C ₆ H ₅ -C ₆ H ₄ -	-	8	14	16	15	8
3g	2-OH-C ₆ H ₄ -	-	22	12	12	10	10
3h	4-OH-C ₆ H ₄ -	-	18	10	14	10	12
3i	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	-	17	15	14	12	16
3j	3-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	-	12	11	8	14	16
Ampicillin	-	-	20	24	22	12	0
Amoxicillin	-	-	21	24	25	18	0
Norfloxacin	-	-	18	17	18	18	0
Benzyl penicillin	-	-	10	18	15	15	0
Greseofulvin	-	-	0	0	0	0	24

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Thin layer chromatography using silica gel G (E. Merck) plates was used to access the reactions and purity of the synthesized compounds. All the products have been characterized by elemental analysis, IR, ¹H NMR and mass spectral study. IR spectra were recorded on Shimadzu FTIR-8400 spectrophotometer in KBr disc and noteworthy absorption levels (cm⁻¹) are listed. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on Bruker spectrometer (300 MHz) using TMS as an internal standard, chemical shift in δ ppm. Mass spectra were determined using direct inlet probe on a GCMS-QP2010 mass spectrometer, elemental analysis were performed on a Carlo Erba EA 1108 elemental analyzer.

General procedure for preparation of (2E)-1-(3,5-

dibromo-4-methoxyphenyl)-3-aryl-prop-2-en-1-ones (1a-j) :

A solution of 3,5-dibromo-4-methoxyacetophenone (3.08 g, 0.01 mol) and different arylaldehyde (0.01 mol) in methanol (25 ml) was stirred at room temperature for 24 h in presence of catalytic amount of 40% KOH (0.5 ml). The resulting solution was poured onto crushed ice, thus the separated solid was filtered and crystallized from ethanol to give analytical pure products.

General procedure for preparation of 1-acetyl-3-(3,5-dibromo-4-methoxyphenyl)-5-aryl-4,5-dihydro-1H-pyrazoles (2a-j) :

A mixture of (2E)-1-(3,5-dibromo-4-methoxyphenyl)-3-aryl-prop-2-en-1-ones (**1a-j**), (0.01 mol) in acetic acid (25 ml) and hydrazine hydrate (0.5 g, 0.01 mol) was refluxed for 7-8 h. The resulting content was poured

Scheme 1

onto crushed ice, filtered and crystallized from ethanol. Physical and spectral data of all the synthesized compound are summarize as under.

2a : 1-Acetyl-3-(3,5-dibromo-4-methoxyphenyl)-5-(3-bromophenyl)-4,5-dihydro-1*H*-pyrazole : Yield 68%; m.p. 158 °C; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) 1642 (C=C), 1585 (C=N), 1269 (C–O–C), 590 (C–Br), 1566 (C=C), 3070 (C–H); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ 3.89 (3H, s, OCH_3), 3.12 (1H, dd, J 18.0 and 4.8 Hz, pyrazoline- H_A), 3.42 (1H, dd, J 18.0 and 11.7 Hz, pyrazolines- H_B), 7.21 (6H, m, Ar-H), 2.86 (3H, s, CO- CH_3), 5.28 (1H, dd, J 4.8 and 11.7 Hz, chiral-H) (Found : C, 40.63; H, 2.93; N, 5.23. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{15}\text{Br}_3\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$ (531.03) : C, 40.71; H, 2.85; N, 5.28%).

2b : 1-Acetyl-3-(3,5-dibromo-4-methoxyphenyl)-5-(2-chlorophenyl)-4,5-dihydro-1*H*-pyrazole : Yield 72%; m.p. 108 °C; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) 1648 (C=C), 1605 (C=N), 1223 (C–O–C), 584 (C–Br), 1580 (C=C), 734 (C–Cl), 3022 (C–H); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ 3.94 (3H, s, OCH_3), 3.09 (1H, dd, J 16.9 and 6.7 Hz, pyrazoline- H_A), 3.39 (1H, dd, J 16.9 and 11.9 Hz, pyrazolines- H_B), 7.30 (6H, m, Ar-H), 2.92 (3H, s, CO- CH_3), 5.23 (1H, dd, J 6.8 and 12.0 Hz, chiral-H) (Found : C, 44.66; H, 3.95; N, 5.73. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{15}\text{Br}_2\text{ClN}_2\text{O}_2$ (486.58) : C, 44.43; H, 3.11; N, 5.76%).

2c : 1-Acetyl-3-(3,5-dibromo-4-methoxyphenyl)-5-(4-*N,N*-dimethylaminophenyl)-4,5-dihydro-1*H*-pyrazole : Yield 68%; m.p. 178 °C; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) 1654 (C=C),

1595 (C=N), 1272 (C–O–C), 584 (C–Br), 1586 (C=C), 3022 (C–H); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ 3.92 (3H, s, OCH_3), 3.08 (1H, dd, J 17.2 and 5.8 Hz, pyrazoline- H_A), 3.59 (1H, dd, J 17.1 and 11.6 Hz, pyrazoline- H_B), 6.9 (6H, m, Ar-H), 2.82 (3H, s, CO- CH_3), 5.26 (1H, dd, J 5.8 and 11.5 Hz, chiral-H), 2.91 (6H, s, $\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_2$) (Found : C, 48.54; H, 4.25; N, 8.47. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{21}\text{Br}_2\text{N}_3\text{O}_2$ (495.20) : C, 48.51; H, 4.27; N, 8.49%).

2d : 1-Acetyl-3-(3,5-dibromo-4-methoxyphenyl)-5-(4-methoxyphenyl)-4,5-dihydro-1*H*-pyrazole : Yield 65%; m.p. 75 °C; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) 1630 (C=C), 1542 (C=N), 1248 (C–O–C), 579 (C–Br), 1576 (C=C), 3047 (C–H); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ 3.78 (3H, s, OCH_3), 3.14 (1H, dd, J 17.5 and 6.3 Hz, pyrazoline- H_A), 3.36 (1H, dd, J 17.4 and 10.9 Hz, pyrazolne- H_B), 7.12 (6H, m, Ar-H), 2.89 (3H, s, CO- CH_3), 5.20 (1H, dd, J 6.4 and 10.9 Hz, chiral-H), 3.64 (3H, s, OCH_3) (Found : C, 47.36; H, 3.75; N, 5.84. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{18}\text{Br}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_3$ (482.16) C, 47.33; H, 3.76; N, 5.81%).

2e : 1-Acetyl-3-(3,5-dibromo-4-methoxyphenyl)-5-(2-nitrophenyl)-4,5-dihydro-1*H*-pyrazole : Yield 58%; m.p. 122 °C; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) 1664 (C=C), 1592 (C=N), 1282 (C–O–C), 532 (C–Br), 1496 (C=C), 3036 (C–H); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ 3.92 (3H, s, OCH_3), 3.09 (1H, dd, J 16.7 and 4.9 Hz, pyrazoline- H_A), 3.32 (1H, dd, J 16.8 and 10.7 Hz, pyrazoline- H_B), 7.14 (6H, m, Ar-H), 2.75 (3H, s, CO- CH_3), 5.26 (1H, dd, J 4.7 and 10.6 Hz, chiral-H) (Found : C, 43.46; H, 3.05; N, 8.48. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{15}\text{Br}_2\text{N}_3\text{O}_4$ (497.14) : C, 43.49; H, 3.04; N, 8.45%).

2f : 1-Acetyl-3-(3,5-dibromo-4-methoxyphenyl)-5-(3-phenoxyphenyl)-4,5-dihydro-1*H*-pyrazole : Yield 59%; m.p. 158 °C; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) 1668 (C=C), 1630 (C=N), 1272 (C–O–C), 596 (C–Br), 1526 (C=C), 3062 (C–H); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ 3.82 (3H, s, OCH_3), 2.96 (1H, dd, J 16.9 and 5.6 Hz, pyrazoline- H_A), 3.13 (1H, dd, J 17.0 and 11.3 Hz, pyrazoline- H_B), 7.41 (6H, m, Ar-H), 2.37 (3H, s, CO- CH_3), 5.36 (1H, dd, J 5.7 and 11.3 Hz, chiral-H), 7.9 (5H, m, Ar-H) (Found : C, 52.94; H, 3.68; N, 5.16. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{20}\text{Br}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_3$ (544.23) : C, 52.97; H, 3.70; N, 5.15%).

2g : 1-Acetyl-3-(3,5-dibromo-4-methoxyphenyl)-5-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-4,5-dihydro-1*H*-pyrazole : Yield 58%; m.p. 148 °C; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) 1672 (C=C), 1570 (C=N), 1293 (C–O–C), 532 (C–Br), 1496 (C=C), 3068 (C–H); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ 3.84 (3H, s, OCH_3), 2.98 (1H, dd, J 17.8 and 4.9 Hz, pyrazoline- H_A), 3.31 (1H, dd, J 17.7 and 10.6 Hz, pyrazoline- H_B), 6.91 (6H, m, Ar-H), 2.53 (3H, s, CO- CH_3), 5.32 (1H, dd, J 4.9 and 10.5 Hz,

chiral-H), 9.8 (1H, s, Ar-OH) (Found : C, 46.21; H, 3.46; N, 5.96. Calcd. for $C_{18}H_{16}Br_2N_2O_3$ (468.14) : C, 46.18; H, 3.44; N, 5.98%).

2h : 1-Acetyl-3-(3,5-dibromo-4-methoxyphenyl)-5-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-4,5-dihydro-1*H*-pyrazole : Yield 55%; m.p. 240° C; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) 1634 (C=C), 1580 (C=N), 1281 (C-O-C), 568 (C-Br), 1520 (C=C), 3062 (C-H); 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$) δ 3.81 (3H, s, OCH_3), 2.96 (1H, dd, *J* 17.4 and 6.1 Hz, pyrazoline- H_A), 3.28 (1H, dd, *J* 17.4 and 11.1 Hz, pyrazoline- H_B), 7.24 (6H, m, Ar-H), 2.87 (3H, s, CO- CH_3), 5.62 (1H, dd, *J* 6.2 and 11.0 Hz, chiral-H), 9.9 (1H, s, Ar-OH) (Found : C, 46.21; H, 3.46; N, 5.96. Calcd. for $C_{18}H_{16}Br_2N_2O_3$ (468.14) : C, 46.18; H, 3.44; N, 5.98%).

2i : 1-Acetyl-3-(3,5-dibromo-4-methoxyphenyl)-5-(4-chlorophenyl)-4,5-dihydro-1*H*-pyrazole : Yield 65%; m.p. 109° C; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) 1628 (C=C), 1598 (C=N), 1265 (C-O-C), 586 (C-Br), 619 (C-Cl), 1526 (C=C), 794 (C-Cl), 3078 (C-H); 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$) δ 3.96 (3H, s, OCH_3), 2.89 (1H, dd, *J* 16.6 and 5.3 Hz, pyrazoline- H_A), 3.22 (1H, dd, *J* 16.5 and 10.8 Hz, pyrazoline- H_B), 6.98 (6H, m, Ar-H), 2.97 (3H, s, CO- CH_3), 5.76 (1H, dd, *J* 5.3 and 10.8 Hz, chiral-H) (Found : C, 44.42; H, 3.14; N, 5.79. Calcd. for $C_{18}H_{15}Br_2ClN_2O_2$ (486.58) : C, 44.43; H, 3.11; N, 5.76%).

2j : 1-Acetyl-3-(3,5-dibromo-4-methoxyphenyl)-5-(3-nitrophenyl)-4,5-dihydro-1*H*-pyrazole : Yield 60%; m.p. 258° C; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) 1662 (C=C), 1604 (C=N), 1229 (C-O-C), 589 (C-Br), 1587 (C=C), 3047 (C-H); 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$) δ 3.92 (3H, s, OCH_3), 3.07 (1H, dd, *J* 17.8 and 5.1 Hz, pyrazoline- H_A), 3.28 (1H, dd, *J* 17.9 and 11.5 Hz, pyrazoline- H_B), 7.08 (6H, m, Ar-H), 2.79 (3H, s, CO- CH_3), 5.46 (1H, dd, *J* 5.2 and 11.4 Hz, chiral-H) (Found : C, 43.46; H, 3.09; N, 8.47. Calcd. for $C_{18}H_{15}Br_2N_3O_4$ (497.13) : C, 43.49; H, 3.04; N, 8.45%).

General procedure for preparation of 3-(3,5-dibromo-4-methoxyphenyl)-5-aryl-isoxazoles (3a-j) :

A mixture of (2*E*)-1-(3,5-dibromo-4-methoxyphenyl)-3-aryl-prop-2-en-1-ones (**1a-j**), (0.01 mol), hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.59 g, 0.01 mol), anhydrous sodium acetate (0.739 g, 0.01 mol) and glacial acetic acid (10 ml) in ethanol (25 ml) was refluxed for 7–8 h on oil bath. The resulting mixture was allowed to cool, separated solid was filtered and washed with chilled ethanol. To give afforded products. This was crystallized from ethanol. Physical and spectral data of all the synthesized compound are summarize as under.

3a : 3-(3,5-Dibromo-4-methoxyphenyl)-5-(3-bromophenyl)-isoxazole : Yield 66%; m.p. 113° C; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) 1550 (C=C), 1448 (C=N), 1255 (C-O-C), 619 (C-Br), 850 (N-O), 1522 (C=C), 3058 (C-H); 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$) δ 3.79 (3H, s, OCH_3), 7.48 (1H, s, isoxazole-H), 6.92 (6H, m, Ar-H) (Found : C, 39.32; H, 2.04; N, 2.87. Calcd. for $C_{16}H_{10}Br_3NO_2$ (487.97) : C, 39.38; H, 2.07; N, 2.87%).

3b : 3-(3,5-Dibromo-4-methoxyphenyl)-5-(2-chlorophenyl)-isoxazole : Yield 72%; m.p. 108° C; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) 1531 (C=C), 1452 (C=N), 1252 (C-O-C), 621 (C-Br), 882 (N-O), 1490 (C=C), 786 (C-Cl), 3054 (C-H); 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$) δ 3.87 (3H, s, OCH_3), 7.18 (1H, s, isoxazole-H), 7.96 (6H, m, Ar-H) (Found : C, 43.36; H, 2.24; N, 3.18. Calcd. for $C_{16}H_{10}Br_2ClNO_2$ (443.52) : C, 43.33; H, 2.27; N, 3.16%).

3c : 3-(3,5-Dibromo-4-methoxyphenyl)-5-(4-*N,N*-dimethylphenyl)-isoxazole : Yield 69%; m.p. 112° C; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) 1540 (C=C), 1454 (C=N), 1270 (C-O-C), 702 (C-Br), 847 (N-O), 1512 (C=C), 3056 (C-H); 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$) δ 3.92 (3H, s, OCH_3), 3.04 (6H, s, $N(CH_3)_2$), 7.23 (1H, s, isoxazoles-H), 6.86 (6H, m, Ar-H) (Found : C, 47.86; H, 3.54; N, 6.18. Calcd. for $C_{18}H_{16}Br_2N_2O_2$ (452.14) : C, 47.82; H, 3.57; N, 6.20%).

3d : 3-(3,5-Dibromo-4-methoxyphenyl)-5-(4-methoxyphenyl)-isoxazole : Yield 62%; m.p. 115° C; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) 1520 (C=C), 1462 (C=N), 1270 (C-O-C), 631 (C-Br), 889 (N-O), 1482 (C=C), 3062 (C-H); 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$) δ 3.83 (3H, s, OCH_3), 7.52 (1H, s, isoxazole-H), 6.68 (6H, m, Ar-H), 3.94 (3H, s, Ar- OCH_3) (Found : C, 46.47; H, 2.94; N, 3.18. Calcd. for $C_{17}H_{13}Br_2NO_3$ (439.09) : C, 46.50; H, 2.98; N, 3.19%).

3e : 3-(3,5-Dibromo-4-methoxyphenyl)-5-(2-nitrophenyl)-isoxazole : Yield 63%; m.p. 101° C; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) 1529 (C=C), 1460 (C=N), 1302 (C-O-C), 628 (C-Br), 872 (N-O), 1490 (C=C), 3057 (C-H); 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$) δ 3.78 (3H, s, OCH_3), 7.59 (1H, s, isoxazole-H), 7.36 (6H, m, Ar-H) (Found : C, 42.34; H, 2.24; N, 6.18. Calcd. for $C_{16}H_{10}Br_2N_2O_4$ (454.07) : C, 42.32; H, 2.22; N, 6.17%).

3f : 3-(3,5-Dibromo-4-methoxyphenyl)-5-(3-phenoxyphenyl)-isoxazole : Yield 59%; m.p. 80° C; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) 1548 (C=C), 1446 (C=N), 1256 (C-O-C), 627 (C-Br), 858 (N-O), 1496 (C=C), 3062 (C-H); 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$) δ 3.68 (3H, s, OCH_3), 7.54 (1H, s, isoxazole-H), 7.82 (11H, m, Ar-H) (Found : C, 52.69; H, 3.06; N, 2.78. Calcd. for $C_{22}H_{15}Br_2NO_3$ (501.17) : C, 52.72; H, 3.02; N, 2.79%).

3g : 3-(3,5-Dibromo-5-methoxyphenyl)-5-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-isoxazole : Yield 58%; m.p. 164° C; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) 1544 (C=C), 1472 (C=N), 1248 (C-O-C), 638 (C-Br), 862 (N-O), 1510 (C=C), 3047 (C-H); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 3.74 (3H, s, OCH₃), 7.28 (1H, s, isoxazole-H), 6.98 (6H, m, Ar-H), 9.6 (1H, s, Ar-OH) (Found : C, 45.24; H, 2.62; N, 3.28. Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₁Br₂NO₃ (425.07) : C, 45.21; H, 2.61; N, 3.30%).

3h : 3-(3,5-Dibromo-4-methoxyphenyl)-5-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-isoxazole : Yield 55%; m.p. 155° C; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) 1563 (C=C), 1480 (C=N), 1252 (C-O-C), 629 (C-Br), 873 (N-O), 1526 (C=C), 3042 (C-H); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 3.72 (3H, s, OCH₃), 7.26 (1H, s, isoxazole-H), 7.12 (6H, m, Ar-H), 9.8 (1H, s, Ar-OH) (Found : C, 45.24; H, 2.62; N, 3.28. Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₁Br₂NO₃ (425.07) : C, 45.21; H, 2.61; N, 3.30%).

3i : 3-(3,5-Dibromo-4-methoxyphenyl)-5-(4-chlorophenyl)-isoxazole : Yield 61%; m.p. 110° C; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) 1574 (C=C), 1464 (C=N), 1246 (C-O-C), 617 (C-Br), 881 (N-O), 1476 (C=C), 788 (C-Cl), 3068 (C-H); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 3.86 (3H, s, OCH₃), 7.24 (1H, s, isoxazole-H), 7.23 (6H, m, Ar-H) (Found : C, 43.29; H, 2.26; N, 3.18. Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₀Br₂ClNO₂ (443.52) : C, 43.33; H, 2.27; N, 3.16%).

3j : 3-(3,5-Dibromo-4-methoxyphenyl)-5-(3-nitrophenyl)-isoxazole : Yield 60%; m.p. 125° C; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) 1577 (C=C), 1454 (C=N), 1256 (C-O-C), 621 (C-Br), 884 (N-O), 1474 (C=C), 3056 (C-H); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 3.76 (3H, s, OCH₃), 7.82 (1H, s, isoxazole-H), 7.63 (6H, m, Ar-H) (Found : C, 42.30; H, 2.24; N, 6.18. Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₀Br₂N₂O₄ (454.07) : C, 42.32; H, 2.22; N, 6.17%).

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